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**TO STUDY THE NEED OF GUIDANCE THROUGH WHATSAPP SOCIAL NETWORKING
TECHNOLOGY**

Education

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Abstract –

The information communication technology education is growing at an incredible rate. The need of guidance through whatsapp social networking technology, the attitude of students teacher towards guidance has been reaction with computers on our everyday lives is monumental, through taken for granted. Every time we make a bank deposit ,purchase items on a credit card, pay an insurance premium or a rent a video movie, innumerable computer operations, are involved. The study explored the need of social networking technology among which are Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and Whatsapp and communication platforms such as Google talk and explore the usage of social networking technologies in higher education by focusing on the teacher training. In modern society raising the educational higher level of the average citizen. The role of social networking technology and internet tools is fundamentally changing the way we live and work. The social networking technology were need for teacher training purposes, these were mostly used to discuss guidance Connectivity was also a challenge for quite a good number of respondents especially trainee teachers in training institution. The lifelong learning sector is no exception with information communication technology having a major impact on teaching and learning.

Keywords:- *Guidance ,Teacher Training, Social Networking Technology, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube , Whatsapp, information communication technology.*

Introduction:-

The knowledge based society is very important in the 21st century. Computer are growing in popularity rapidly. The information communication networking technology is growing at an incredible rate .The guidance is one of the major application of psychology in education. It enables the individual to solve educational,vocational and psychological problems. Guidance refers to a process of assisting the individual to develop student-teachers personality, mind and character and to help in achieving maximum educational, vocational and personal adjustments. Through social networking technology is easy to explain the guidance is a process of learning helping and affecting changes in an student-teacher.. The role of information communication networking technology and internet tools is fundamentally changing the way we live and work. The lifelong learning sector is no exception with information networking technology having a major impact on teaching and learning. It is an close relationship between guidance has been an inseparable part of the educative process. Guidance refers to a service which should be involved in the teaching situation with the help of social networking technology. The social networking technology has the potential to improve student learning. Guidance refers to a process in which the student-teacher is helped to make a decision, to make a important matter like a programme in the teacher training institution getting employment, planning for life.

Objectives:-

- 1.To study the need of guidance through social networking technology for student-teacher.
- 2.To find the communication of guidance through social networking technology among student-teacher.
- 3.To explore the benefits of social networking technology in guidance.
- 4.To suggest the social networking technology is a communication media of guidance for student-teacher.

Methodology

The sample was undertaken from both faculty members and all admitted trainee students during the year 2013-2014. Out of the 35 teacher training institutions, 04 were drawn into the sample obtained through the convenience sampling method. Of the 380 registered students, only 110 made it into the sample drawn proportionally through the stratified random sampling. There are 12 statements in the questionnaire included a combination of both structured and semi-structured questions., a survey questionnaire used for the purpose of this study, which contained both open and closed ended questions.

Collection of Data :-

The investigators personally contacted all the student-teachers who were studying in B.Ed. In the year 2013-2014 and distributed the questionnaire to them after a polite request. Only 110 trainee students return the questionnaire and supplied the information for the study.

Analysis and Conclusion :-

A total of 110 trainee students participated in the study and the distribution of the participants is shown in Table I below.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Participants .

Media	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage	Average
	Problems concerning emotional and mental health	90	81.81	
	Individual in making family adjustment	80	72.72	

Whatsapp	Social adjustment	100	90.00
	Clouding adjustment	75	68.19
	Progress	65	59.09
	Working with community	85	77.27
	Vocational Problems	66	60.00
	Communication	65	43.33
	Physical and health education	55	36.67
	Creativity and personality development programme	90	81.81
	Educational aids, Internal examination	98	89.09
	student achievement	65	43.33

Figure 1:- 110 trainee students participated in the study and the distribution of the participants

With regards to skill acquired by student-teacher through need of social networking technology ,

1. It was found out that most (90.00 %) of the trainee teachers suggested social adjustment as a result of using social networking technology .
2. Problems concerning emotional and mental health (81.81 %) student-teachers refers to choice of method and mode of communication.
3. Individual in making family adjustment (72.72%), it emerged out that the majority of student-teacher use social networking technology for teacher training that is in general and for specific school work.
4. Clouding adjustment Progress(68.19%), Working with community(77.27%), Vocational Problems (60.00),Communication(43.33%), Physical and health education(36.67%), Creativity and personality

development Programme(81.81%),Educational aids Internal examination, (89.09%),
student achievement(43.33%)

This was followed by WhatsApp social networking technology is capable of carrying different kinds of symbols through WhatsApp like speech,music,sound effects,pictures,diagrams and mores.WhatsApp can bring the world guidance of reality to the individual either through live telecast. WhatsApp enables the students to see and hear for themselves and it is taken to be the most believable news source.WhatsApp moreover can become a great equalizer of educational opportunities . WhatsApp can be both instructive as well as enjoyable. It provides an interesting and exciting change and furnishes some of the variety that is the spice of guidance.

Suggestion:-

From the research findings, the social networking technology Whatsapp provides some of the barriers in Problems concerning emotional and mental health, Individual in making family adjustment, Social adjustment, Clouding adjustment, Working with community,Individual progress, Communication, Physical and health education, Creativity and personality development programme, Educational aids, Internal examination, student achievement.WhatsApp facilitates a school to share its best teachers rather than rationing them.It acts as a supplementary enrichment for it brings the latest information for guidance.Thus we can say that WhatsApp is a very powerful medium and if properly integrated with guidance,it can definitely make the personality more effective.

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